

SAYYID SHARIF JURJANI'S "TA'RIFAT" LITHOGRAPHIC EDITIONS

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Abstract. This article is dedicated to the study of lithographic editions of Ta'rifat, a work by Sayyid Sharif Jurjani. Although no manuscript copies of this work are preserved in Uzbekistan's major collections, the text remains influential, with several lithographic editions published during the 19th and early 20th centuries. The article presents detailed information about these editions, including publication locations, publishers, number of pages, sizes, and the collections in which they are currently held.

Keywords: Ta'rifat, Sayyid Sharif Jurjani, lithograph, manuscript, Istanbul, Egypt, St. Petersburg, Oriental Studies Institute, history of the book, scientific heritage

Introduction. Sayyid Sharif Jurjani's Ta'rifat is one of the most important sources in the Islamic scientific tradition. Despite its widespread circulation in earlier times, no manuscript copies of the work are currently available in Uzbekistan's major repositories, including the Abu Rayhan Beruni Institute of Oriental Studies. For this reason, lithographic editions of the text — which carry significant historical and academic value — are the primary focus of this study. This paper provides detailed information about these lithographs preserved at the Institute and in other collections.

Materials. The research is based on the following primary materials:

Lithographic editions of Ta'rifat housed at the Institute of Oriental Studies of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Editions from the Hamid Sulaymonov private collection

Archival data including inventory numbers, publication years, locations, publishers, sizes, and page counts of each copy

Methods. The study employs analytical and comparative methods. Various lithographic editions are analyzed in terms of their chronological, geographical, and physical characteristics (such as format and page count). Special attention is given to historical and regional contexts, particularly regarding publication centers in Istanbul, Egypt, and St. Petersburg.

Results. Over 15 lithographic editions of Ta'rifat were identified.

The majority were published in Istanbul; others were printed in Egypt and St. Petersburg.

Most editions were published between 1866 and 1900.

Common publishers included Orif Afandi, Shirkati Sihofiyya, Matba'a-i Husayn, and Dār al-Sa'āda.

The size and length of the books vary, although their content remains largely consistent.

Some editions include supplements, such as *Istilahat-i Sufiyya* (“Sufi Terminologies”).

Discussion. Although *Taʿrifat* was written by a scholar associated with the Islamic intellectual tradition in Central Asia, manuscript copies are not found in local collections, including those of the Beruni Institute. Nevertheless, the work’s wide influence is confirmed through the existence of numerous lithographic editions.

The following are a few notable examples among the copies examined:

Examples of Lithographic Editions

Taʿrifat, Inv. no. 6878 – Egypt, 1889, 120 pages, 24.5×15 cm

Taʿrifat-i Sayyid, Inv. no. 12315 – Istanbul, 1900, 215 pages, 23.5×15.5 cm

Taʿrifat-i Sayyid, Inv. no. 12025; 12590 – Istanbul, 1889, 188 pages, 22.5×15 cm

Taʿrifat-i Sayyid, Inv. no. 6843 – Istanbul, 1900, 215 pages, 26×15 cm

Taʿrifat-i Sayyidi, Inv. no. 6463 – Istanbul, n.d., 125 pages, 24×15 cm

Taʿrifat-i Sayyid Sharif, Inv. nos. 8433; 15510; 17243 – Istanbul, 1889, 128 pages, 23×16 cm

Taʿrifat-i Sayyid Sharif, Inv. nos. 8488; 8613; 8614; 8580; 15655 – Istanbul, 1900, 177 pages, 24×16 cm

Taʿrifat-i Sayyid Sharif, Inv. no. 6984 – Istanbul, 1900, 175 pages, 15×23 cm

Taʿrifat-i Mir Sayyid Sharif, Inv. nos. 10248; 17088 – St. Petersburg, 1897, 144 pages, 15×22 cm

Taʿrifat-i Sayyidi maʿa Istilahāt-i Sufiyya, Inv. no. 6450 – Istanbul, 1866, 175+12 pages, 26×16 cm

Taʿrifat-i Sayyidi, Inv. nos. 8448; 15871 – Istanbul, 1890, 175 pages, 15×23 cm

Additional lithographs were found in the Hamid Sulaymonov Collection at the Oriental Studies Institute, including editions from 1318 and 1327 AH, mostly printed in Istanbul.

The dominance of Istanbul in this list reflects the city’s status as the intellectual center of the Islamic world during the Ottoman period. Cairo (Misr) also hosted some early publications due to the establishment of Arabic printing presses there. Publications from St. Petersburg were produced by Tatar scholars, as evidenced by publisher names.

Conclusion. Though no manuscript copies of *Taʿrifat* exist in Uzbekistan’s current collections, its scholarly legacy is preserved through multiple lithographic editions published across Istanbul, Egypt, and Russia in the 19th and early 20th centuries. These editions not only indicate the enduring popularity and influence of

Jurjani's work but also reflect its recognition across various Islamic intellectual centers. Future research should focus on digitizing these lithographs, conducting comparative textual analysis, and incorporating them into broader academic discourse.

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